

Size and factors of the motherhood penalty in the labour market: A meta-analysis

Irina E. Kalabikhina ¹, Polina O. Kuznetsova ^{1,2}, Sofiia A. Zhuravleva ¹

¹ Faculty of Economics, M. V. Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, 119991, Russia

² Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration, Moscow, 119571, Russia

Received 24 February 2024 ♦ Accepted 22 April 2024 ♦ Published 12 September 2024

Citation: Kalabikhina IE, Kuznetsova PO, Zhuravleva SA (2024) Size and factors of the motherhood penalty in the labour market: A meta-analysis. Population and Economics 8(2):178-205. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.8.e121438>

Abstract

Numerous empirical studies show that mothers are often paid less than women without children, who have similar profiles. This paper presents the results of a meta-analysis of existing estimates of the motherhood wage penalty (over 2,000 estimates on data for 38 countries).

A statistically significant publication bias was found towards a higher penalty estimate. However, the motherhood penalty persists even after correcting for the bias. Many sources of heterogeneity of the current estimates of the motherhood penalty were shown to exist, including technical characteristics of the model, precision of the estimate, and inclusion of information on women's human capital, employment, and other individual characteristics in the regression model.

The analysis confirmed the significance of such sources of the motherhood penalty as losses caused by employment interruptions and underinvestment in human capital, exchange of part of the wage for more convenient working conditions, reduced work effort, including due to high involvement in unpaid domestic work. The hypothesis of mothers' lower productivity is not supported.

Controlling for regional variables revealed a relatively higher motherhood penalty in Western Europe and the United States and a relatively lower one in Latin America. This provides some empirical evidence in favour of the study's hypothesis of a possible relationship between the size of the motherhood penalty and fertility concentration. In countries with a significant heterogeneity in the distribution of women by the number of births (high prevalence of childlessness and/or multiple children), employers may favour smaller gender pay gaps along with a higher motherhood penalty.

Keywords

motherhood penalty; family wage gap; meta-analysis; meta-regression; fertility; fertility concentration

JEL codes: J13, J16, J31

Introduction

The gender pay gap is one of the most persistent systemic problems of modern societies with differently organised socio-economic systems and welfare economies. This pervasive and long-standing phenomenon not only exacerbates problems of social injustice and inequality of opportunity, but also causes significant economic losses, both at the macro level (economic losses due to inefficient use of women's labour) and at the micro level (lower incomes of female households and increased risks of poverty and income inequality) (Strengmann-Kuhn 2007; Gradín et al. 2010).

Gender wage differentials are caused by horizontal and vertical segregation ("male" vs. "female" occupations; "sticky floor" or "glass ceiling"), lagging human capital of women, and direct gender discrimination in the labour market (Mincer and Polachek 1974; Stanley and Jarrel 1998; Blau et al. 2013; Levanon and Grusky 2016). The reasons lie in the high involvement of women in the care economy, i.e. unpaid labour to care for children and vulnerable household members, as well as in household management. As a result, it is women who choose jobs that allow them to better balance family and work, but with lower pay and fewer career opportunities (Becker 1985; Goldin 2014). Spending time on household chores and caring for vulnerable household members may lead to women's lower productivity at work. Besides, the allocation of women's and men's time to paid and unpaid work has an impact on women's human capital accumulation and direct gender discrimination in the labour market.

As a consequence, the parental status is an important factor in wages. There are significant wage differentials in many countries between mothers and women without children, and these differentials still persist when controlling for women's human capital, employment patterns, and individual unobservable characteristics and considering social and cultural norms of their respective countries (Kleven et al. 2019; Cortés and Pan 2023).

There is a widespread method of measuring the motherhood penalty by using the coefficient for the motherhood variable (number of children, presence of children, or presence of children of certain birth orders) in the Mincer wage equation¹. The number of studies containing such estimates is growing rapidly. Further complicating aggregate estimates of the penalty is the publication bias arising from the inclination of authors and editors to conform to the prevailing scholarly theory, which in this case is that a significant motherhood penalty is real.

A traditional literature review is not sufficient to handle the large number of estimates, which are obtained using similar but often significantly different regression models. Instead, researchers are increasingly turning to meta-analysis or quantitative literature review methods that allow estimating the true effect of motherhood on wages controlling for publication bias and heterogeneity in the methods and models used to estimate the penalty (Stanley and Doucouliagos 2012).

This paper aims to quantitatively analyze the current research literature on the size of the motherhood penalty. In estimating the penalty, we considered technical specifications of the regression models, specificity of the sets of independent factors used, and the possible presence of publication bias.

¹ The Mincer equation is a model of the relationship between the logarithm of wages and education and experience. In the basic version, the independent variables include the number of years of education and the number of years of work experience. When estimating the motherhood penalty, the list of wage factors is expanded to include the motherhood variable.

We incorporate the experience of two earlier meta-reviews of the motherhood penalty (Cukrowska-Torzewska and Matysiak 2020; de Linde Leonard and Stanley 2020), mostly based on the estimates for the US and the EU. Our contribution is that we significantly expand the sample by adding many new studies on the motherhood penalty. By now, the geography of studies has expanded significantly. Whereas previously data from the US and the EU were mainly analysed, at this time, a significant share of the estimates pertain to other countries or regions, including China, Latin America, Turkey, Russia, etc. A wider geography of research increases the chances of better understanding the role of the type of economic relations, social policies, socio-cultural and demographic characteristics in the estimation of the motherhood penalty. Another feature of our study is the expanded set of explanatory factors, which is possible with the increase in the sample of motherhood penalty estimates.

The paper is structured as follows. First, while briefly reviewing the current scholarly literature, we discuss the causes of the motherhood penalty in the context of existing theories. Then we describe the database and the research method used and present the findings. Finally, we discuss the results obtained and build hypotheses for further research.

Gender discrimination in the labour market and the motherhood penalty

Significant gender wage differentials, which are often not explainable by observable objective individual characteristics of workers, are found everywhere, regardless of the level of development or the prevailing socio-economic model. Discriminatory gender wage differentials cause macro-level economic losses due to inefficient use of women's labour by reducing their labour activity and returns on their human capital compared to optimal values (Cain 1986; Cuberes et al. 2016).

Another important consequence of gender wage differentials is their contribution to income inequality and poverty due to reduced income of female households. It has been shown on the EU data that hypothetical removal of gender discrimination would significantly reduce poverty, especially in households where the main source of income is the wage of female workers (Gradín et al. 2010). Wage losses of women with children increase poverty risks not only for women and children, but also for men living in their households (Strengmann-Kuhn 2007). Moreover, child's well-being suffers from gender wage gaps. It is not just about income: children lack other resources, too, which negatively affects their future human capital and can contribute to chronic poverty, poor health, and lack of education, which could be passed on from generation to generation (Wang and Cheng 2021).

In the context of population ageing and decreasing resources of intra-family support in the post-industrial society, another negative effect of gender discrimination in the labour market is increasingly important: lower wages lead to lower pensions thus reducing women's chances for a financially secure old age (Gough 2001; Warren et al. 2001).

The decomposition of the wage gap indicates at least three determinants of the differentials: 1) horizontal segregation ("female" vs. "male" occupations, a higher proportion of women in the poorly protected informal employment sector, etc.) and vertical segregation (differences in the representation of women and men at levels of the vertical career ladder) (Blau et al. 2013; Pan 2015; Cortés and Pan 2018); 2) women's human capital lag, for example, due to a relatively low level of education (Mincer and Polachek 1974; Becker 1985; Blau

and Kahn 2017); 3) direct gender discrimination in the labour market, where employers pay different wages for the same work (Stanley and Jarrel 1998; Black and Strahan 2001; Flabbi 2010).

The reasons for the above circumstances lie in the large involvement of women in unpaid labour to care for children, the elderly and other vulnerable family members, as well as in household management. Despite the gradual levelling of differences, a significant gender gap persists (Bianchi et al. 2000; Blau and Kahn 2017; Kleven et al. 2019).

Such discrimination makes women choose jobs with characteristics that allow them to better balance family and work, but with lower remuneration and fewer opportunities for labour market participation and career advancement. This, in turn, negatively affects the amount of time they can afford for paid work (overtime hours, business trips, training, etc.) and possibly the work intensity in the workplace (Becker 1985; Goldin 2014; Angelov et al. 2016; Budig and England 2001; Gallen 2024). Moreover, even the level of human capital is related to the initial opportunities to acquire it. Obviously, current or anticipated future child-rearing concerns limit such opportunities (Mincer and Polachek 1974; Becker 1985; Klepinger et al. 1999).

Direct gender discrimination in the labour market also stems from employer preferences based ultimately on the allocation of time to paid versus unpaid work (Stanley and Jarrel 1998; Black and Strahan 2001; Correll et al. 2007; Flabbi 2010).

Thus, the parental status (being part of the care economy) is an important wage factor. This was first noticed in the studies of gender wage gap, which brought about a new dynamic and evolving area of research, which is the estimation of the so-called motherhood penalty. In many countries, there are significant wage differentials between mothers and women without children, and these differentials persist even when controlling for the indicators of women's human capital, their employment characteristics, and individual unobservable characteristics. More than two-thirds of the gender wage gap is explainable by different effects of having children on working men and working women in the US (Cortés and Pan 2023). The effect of the motherhood penalty on the wage gap has been documented in countries with different labour market policies, e.g., the US with its more liberal policies and Denmark with its more social approach to labour policy (Kleven et al. 2019), as well as in countries and regions with different cultural backgrounds, e.g., the more traditional Western Germany and the more egalitarian, due to its socialist past, Eastern Germany (Jessen 2022).

The literature identifies several main reasons for the motherhood penalty. *The theory of compensating differentials* suggests that mothers choose those occupations and positions that allow a better balance between work and childcare. However, such more favourable conditions come with lower wages, hence the motherhood penalty (Glass 2004; Nielsen et al. 2004). To test the hypothesis that compensating differentials contribute to the motherhood penalty, the multiple meta-regression model can include information on whether certain characteristics of women's employment, such as industry, employer ownership type, and size (presence of appropriate regressors in the models) were considered in estimating the penalty.

Another reason for the motherhood penalty is *selection into motherhood or employment*, which complements the theory of compensating differentials. Mothers and non-mothers may differ in their characteristics even before having children, and therefore self-selection into motherhood occurs for those women who are paid lower wages because of their characteristics (Lundberg and Rose 2000). Self-selection into employment accounted for in the wage calculation using the Heckman correction is similar in nature to selection into motherhood. The meta-analysis can technically take into account information on whether the

estimates of the motherhood penalty were controlled for selection into motherhood and/or employment. If the use of special procedures to account for selection into motherhood or employment in the calculations leads to a significant reduction in the estimates, then we can conclude that such selectivity is indeed one of the mechanisms of the motherhood penalty.

The mechanism based on *human capital theory* has been extensively studied (Becker 1985), whereby mothers' wages are lower than those of women without children because mothers lose out to other women in human capital accumulation due to their employment interruptions because of childbirth and childrearing (Lundberg and Rose 2000; Gangl and Ziefle 2009). The multiple meta-regression analysis can be used to test the hypothesis that mothers lose out on human capital using data on the presence of information on various human capital characteristics in the motherhood penalty estimation model. If the inclusion of the variables for education, work experience, tenure, and employment interruptions in the Mincer equation significantly reduces the estimated penalty, then we can conclude that a loss / lack of human capital does contribute to the motherhood penalty.

The reasons for the motherhood penalty to exist are also studied by the *effort theory* (Becker 1985). Since mothers are committed to a number of childcare responsibilities, women with children tend to invest less effort at work than women without children, which explains lower wages (Budig and Hodges 2010).

The hypothesis of a significant contribution of work effort to the motherhood penalty can be tested *separately for productivity and for hours worked* by using information on the type of regression estimation model: if the meta-estimate of the motherhood penalty decreases when using a fixed effects model, all other things being equal, then we can conclude that mothers are indeed less productive than other women (i.e. controlling for unobservable characteristics, including those related to productivity, results in a reduced motherhood penalty). As for information on the number of working hours, there are a number of ways in which this can be accounted for in the meta-analysis. For instance, hourly wages could be introduced, or information on the number of working hours could be added to the model. In particular, introducing hourly wages instead of weekly, monthly, or annual wages reduces the penalty (de Linde Leonard and Stanley 2020).

Further, *discrimination by employers* against mothers may result in the motherhood penalty (Cuddy et al. 2004; Correll et al. 2007). However, analysis of discrimination in most empirical studies is limited due to the difficulty of quantifying this factor. Typically, an unexplained portion of the gender wage gap would be attributed to discrimination (Budig and England 2001; Oshchepkov 2006). In this meta-analysis, pure discrimination is difficult to identify because it is usually determined through a decomposition procedure that requires estimation of the wage equation not only for the female sample, but also for subsamples of mothers and women without children.

Apart from the above reasons, *institutional and cultural characteristics* of various countries or regions may also impact the motherhood penalty (Budig et al. 2016; Cukrowska-Torzewska and Lovasz 2020). Due to such specific characteristics, the size of motherhood penalty may differ significantly from one country to another, all other things being equal. One of the objectives of this study is to maximise the geographical spread and the time period of motherhood penalty estimation. In this case, the geographical spread and the period of estimation will serve as the approximating variables of differences by the types of social policy and welfare economy, and other institutional and socio-cultural differences.

Sample generation

Article Search

The first step in the meta-analysis is to search for comparable estimates of the effect under study. The search should be as broad as possible to ensure that the selection of papers does not itself cause a systematic bias in the future meta-estimate. Ideally, the meta-analysis should be performed on the general population of all estimates, or, failing that, at least on a representative sample thereof.

It is not a straightforward process to identify all existing estimates. One has to tighten the search criteria due to a large volume of papers on a given topic. One of the ways to reduce the search space is to introduce restrictions, for example, on the time of publication, estimate type, specification of the econometric model, etc.

The object of search are the estimates of an effect of interest from the corresponding econometric model. For the motherhood penalty, it is a coefficient for the motherhood variable in the Mincer equation of the relationship between the logarithm of wages and the women's individual characteristics.

The sample of papers included in the meta-analysis comprises scholarly studies available in the search databases as of July 2023. There were no other restrictions on the timing of publication. Papers with abstracts and titles in English were considered. All papers included in the final sample for the meta-analysis were found later to have their English versions. Along with journal articles, preprints and book chapters were also considered. The initial list of papers was a merger of the results of two searches in the academic databases Google Scholar and EBSCO. The selection of these databases was determined by the method available to us for automating the retrieving and initial processing of the search query data. We were interested in papers whose titles (when searching in Google Scholar) and abstracts (when searching in EBSCO) contained various combinations of the words: motherhood, penalty, wage, gap, family gap. The exact query for the Google Scholar search was as follows: *allintitle: "motherhood penalty" OR "motherhood wage penalty" OR "family gap" OR "family wage gap."* The same for the EBSCO, *AB (motherhood penalty OR family gap) AND wage AND (child OR children) AND (month OR week OR hour)*. The former search yielded 430 papers and the second one, 633 papers.

Next, a first short list of potentially relevant papers was generated by merging the lists which exhibited considerable overlap in their constituent items – the same paper can be published more than once as a preprint, a journal article in the native language and in English, as well as a book chapter, an opinion column, etc. – and totally irrelevant material, such as papers on biology. The authors then went through all the shortlisted papers to select those that contained tabulated data on the size of motherhood penalty derived from the wage equation. We were only interested in studies that contained information on the significance of such estimates².

We then added a small set of papers from two earlier meta-reviews, (Cukrowska-Torzewska and Matysiak 2020) and (de Linde Leonard and Stanley 2020), which did not turn up in our search results. These were typically papers with catchy, unusual titles that were difficult to track down through formal search on the title words.

² For example, the study (Karabchuk et al. 2021), which yielded a substantial number of results, was excluded for Russia because it did not address the significance of the estimates.

Generation of a quantitative research base

The final list to be found in the electronic annex includes 98 papers. Two of them (Agüero et al. 2012; Agüero et al. 2020) provide estimates organised according to groups of countries (namely, low- and middle-income countries), therefore both papers were subsequently excluded. Next, we selected 2,055 estimates of motherhood penalty from those papers. By the region of the study, the distribution of penalty estimates was as follows: Western Europe 14%, Central and Eastern Europe 14%, Northern Europe 7%, Southern Europe 6%, the USA 38%, other developed English-speaking countries 10%, Latin America 6%, others 4%. A diverse group of other countries (India, China, Turkey, South Africa, South Korea, Japan) could not be further disaggregated due to a low total number of studies.

The midpoint of the observation period was in the 1980s or before in 14% of the cases, in the 1990s in 42% of the cases, in the 2000s in 35% of the cases, and in the 2010s in 9% of the cases.

It should be noted that the selection of estimates for the meta-review is also contingent upon the researcher. In a number of cases, we screened out some of the estimates included in earlier meta-reviews.

First, we excluded studies employing samples that were excessively specific, for example, library staff in the study (Kelley et al., 2020). The inclusion of estimates for such samples may subsequently distort the results of the meta-analysis because the characteristics of women in such samples may be very different from those of the general female population. In addition, we did not consider penalty estimates for CV experiments, which are common in research (see, for example, (Correll et al., 2007)), as we were interested in the actual observed wage ratio of mothers to other women, rather than the hypothetical one.

Another reason for screening out some estimates was uniqueness of the methods used. For example, in the paper (Davies and Pierre 2005), in addition to conventional models, used models of earnings growth, which examine changes in the logarithm of earnings as the number of children changes from 0 to 1 year, from 0 to 2 years, and so on, as well as when the parenthood status changes in a given year, etc.

Finally, we excluded from the sample the quintile (percentile) regression results, which are often found in the literature on motherhood penalty estimation, because we believe that there is no satisfactory method of selecting a single result for the overall sample across multiple quintile (percentile) models.

The list of papers included in the meta-analysis is presented in Supplementary material 1 (Papers included in the meta-analysis). The data set on which the regression meta-analysis was performed is presented in Dataset for meta-analysis “The motherhood penalty’s size and factors” (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13710305>).

Quantitative research methodology

Publication bias (a simple regression meta-analysis)

Publication bias is a major problem for meta-estimation. The fact is that average or weighted average estimates of the collected values of the estimated effect (in our case, the motherhood penalty), as a rule, produce a biased estimate, and the estimate is biased towards a stronger effect. Not all studies on a certain topic end up being published, and the papers whose results are more consistent with the currently prevailing theory (in our case, the theory that there exists a significant motherhood penalty) are more likely to be published. The consequence of the bias is, on average, higher estimates of the effect under study for papers with higher

standard errors (de Linde Leonard and Stanley 2020; Stanley 2008; Stanley and Doucouliagos 2012, 2014, 2017). The publication bias can be estimated as follows:

$$effect_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SE_i + \varepsilon_i, \tag{1}$$

or

$$effect_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SE_i^2 + \varepsilon_i, \tag{2}$$

where β_0 is the estimated effect (in our case, the regression coefficient on the motherhood variable), SE_i is the relevant standard error.

In order to alleviate the publication bias effect, it is recommended to use a weighted linear regression with a weight of $1/SE_i^2$ (Stanley and Doucouliagos 2012), which corresponds to the normalisation of variables from equations (1)-(2) by the value of the standard error SE_i :

$$tvalue_i = \beta_1 + \beta_0 / SE_i + \vartheta_i \tag{3}$$

or

$$tvalue_i = \beta_1 SE_i + \beta_0 / SE_i + \mu_i. \tag{4}$$

The former equation corresponds to the jointed funnel asymmetry and precision effect tests (FAT-PET); the latter, the precision effect estimation with standard errors (PEESE). Both tests check for the presence of a publication bias (significance of the coefficient β_1) and provide an estimate of the corrected effect value (coefficient β_0 in equations (3) and (4)).

Multiple meta-regression analysis

The multiple regression meta-analysis was conducted using three models. We assume that the estimate of the effect under study depends on the value of the estimation error and the characteristics of the methods and data used:

$$effect_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SE_i + \sum_{k=2} \beta_k Z_{ki} + \varepsilon_i, \tag{5}$$

where $effect_i$ is the i -th estimate of the effect under study (in our case, the motherhood penalty), SE_i is the standard error of this estimate, Z_{ki} is the value of the k -th characteristic of this estimate from among various heterogeneity factors, such as the features of the regression model and the data used, publication characteristics, etc.

A weighted least squares method was applied to the baseline model (FAT-PET). For this purpose, the equation was multiplied by the inverse of the standard error of the motherhood penalty estimates, which allows the effect estimates to be corrected for possible heteroscedasticity (heterogeneity) of errors. Error heterogeneity arises because effect estimates have different errors in different studies. The proposed weighting procedure allows for more accurate estimates to be accounted for with higher weights:

$$tvalue_i = \beta_1 + \beta_0 / SE_i + \sum_{k=2} \beta_k Z_{ki} / SE_i + u_i. \tag{6}$$

In the latter model (FAT-PET allowing for citations), in addition to weighting for error precision, we considered the citation impact of the papers from which the estimates of the effect under study were drawn. We estimated the citation impact based on data from the Google Scholar search engine. We took logarithms of the weighting variable to smooth out the over-influence of several papers with very high citation impacts. Another reason for the possible imprecision of the meta-estimation of the effect under study may be the issue of similarity of estimates taken from the same study; therefore, we added error clustering to this model depending on what paper the estimates are derived from.

Another way to account for the possible dependence of the estimates on the author bias and study-specific characteristics is to use fixed-effects models. Therefore, as a third model, we used the baseline fixed-effects model for estimates that were derived from the same study. To check the robustness of the results, we additionally calculated alternative model designs, including unweighted and random-effects models, which are presented in the Annex (Table A2).

Selection of independent variables

For each motherhood penalty estimate, information was collected and entered into the meta-study database about the regression model from which it was derived, including on quality (precision), technical features, specification, along with the time and place of data collection. Table 1 describes the variables included in the regression analysis at the initial stage. Information on summary statistics of the variables included in the final model is presented in Table A1 of the Annex.

Table 1. Variables included in the multiple meta-regression analysis

Variable	Definition
Specificity of the estimation method	
<i>fixed effects</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the estimate is obtained using the fixed effects method</i>
<i>other panel methods</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the estimate is obtained using a method other than least squares or fixed effects</i>
<i>selection procedure</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the estimate is obtained allowing for selection into employment (Heckman procedure) or selection into motherhood</i>
<i>panel data</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model considers panel data (for several years)</i>
<i>hourly wage</i>	<i>Equals 1 if hourly wage is considered in the model</i>
Definition of the motherhood variable	
<i>presence of children</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model uses a dummy variable of the presence of children</i>
<i>number of children</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model uses a variable of the number of children</i>
<i>one child</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model uses a variable of the presence of one child</i>
Including variables in the model	
<i>Race / ethnicity</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a race/ethnicity variable</i>
<i>Age</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes the age variable</i>
<i>Region</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of the region of the country</i>
<i>Type of settlement</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of the type of settlement (urban, rural)</i>
<i>Marital status</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes the marital status variable</i>
<i>Other household characteristics</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes any other variables of other household characteristics</i>
<i>Education</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes information on the level of education</i>
<i>Work experience or potential work experience</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of work experience or potential work experience, to be calculated from the data on age and number of years of education</i>

Variable	Definition
<i>Tenure</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of the duration of employment at the current job</i>
<i>Employment interruptions</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of employment interruptions (relation to motherhood)</i>
<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes an occupation variable</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of the industry of employment</i>
<i>Trade union</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of trade union membership</i>
<i>Favourable conditions for motherhood</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of the favourable working conditions for mothers (flexible schedule, possibility to work from home, etc.).</i>
<i>Hours worked</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of the number of hours worked</i>
<i>Employer ownership (public or private)</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of the type of employer ownership</i>
<i>Informal employment</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of informal employment</i>
<i>Employer size</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes a variable of the employer size</i>
Limitations of sampling	
<i>Only private sector employees</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model considers only private sector employees</i>
<i>Only public sector employees</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model considers only public sector employees</i>
<i>Only full-time employment</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model considers only full-time workers</i>
<i>Only high level of education</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model considers only women with a high level of education</i>
<i>Only low level of education</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model considers only women with a low level of education</i>
<i>Only married women</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes only married women</i>
<i>Only single women</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes only single women</i>
<i>Only young women</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes only women aged 40 or below</i>
<i>Only women of a certain race</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the model includes only women of a particular race</i>
Country of estimation	
<i>Southern Europe</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the sample includes women from Southern Europe (Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain)</i>
<i>Western Europe</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the sample includes women from Western Europe (Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Switzerland)</i>
<i>Northern Europe</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the sample includes women from Northern Europe (Denmark, Finland, Norway, Sweden)</i>
<i>USA</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the sample includes women from the USA</i>
<i>Other English-speaking countries</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the sample includes women from an English-speaking country other than the USA (Australia, Canada, Ireland, UK)</i>

Variable	Definition
Central and Eastern Europe	Equals 1 if the sample includes women from Central or Eastern Europe (Czechia, Hungary, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Ukraine)
<i>Latin America</i>	<i>Equals 1 if the sample includes women from Central or South America (Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, Mexico, Peru)</i>
	Decade at midpoint of the period of observations
y1990s	Equals 1 if the estimate is obtained for the period with a midpoint in the 1990s
y2000s	<i>Equals 1 if the estimate is obtained for the period with a midpoint in the 2000s</i>
y2010s	<i>Equals 1 if the estimate is obtained for the period with a midpoint in the 2010s</i>
	Characteristics of the source of estimate
Journal publication	Equals 1 if the estimate is part of a study that is a journal publication
Publication in a Q1 journal	Equals 1 if the estimate is part of a study published in a journal from the first quartile (Q1) according to SJR (Scopus)

Source: authors' calculations

Note: variables in italics are those included in the final model

In the econometric analysis, following the recommendations in (Stanley and Doucouligos 2012), as well as in accordance with the usual practice of other meta-studies, we used the method of step-by-step exclusion of insignificant variables (the so-called general-to-specific method). Inclusion of insignificant variables in the model keeps the estimates unbiased but reduces their efficiency. Also, the robustness of the econometric model may deteriorate due to increased correlation between independent variables. When applying the method of step-by-step exclusion of insignificant variables, a variable among those that do not meet the specified significance criterion (in our case it is $p < 0.1$) is removed at each step from the available set of independent variables (starting with the initial one). The loss of this variable results in the most statistically insignificant deterioration in the model quality. The process stops once such a variable is not found in the available set.

Results

Publication bias

The results of FAT-PET and PEESE tests for publication bias are presented in Table 2. According to the funnel asymmetry test (FAT), the null no-bias hypothesis ($H_0: \beta_1 = 0$, where β_1 is derived from equation (1)) is rejected. Thus, there is a significant publication bias in the sample of collected estimates of motherhood penalty, which results in that lowest-precision estimates (those with higher standard error values) correspond to higher absolute values of the motherhood penalty. At the same time, the precision effect test (PET) rejects the hypothesis that there is no true motherhood penalty ($H_0: \beta_0 = 0$). This suggests that there is a significant motherhood penalty with a sample average of 2.4 per cent, even when accounting

for the actual publication bias. The precision-effect estimation with standard errors (PEESE) leads to similar results: there is a significant publication bias causing an increase in the absolute value of the penalty, but even taking this bias into account, mothers’ wages appear on average 3.2 per cent lower. The penalty estimate allowing for the bias is noticeably lower than the simple sample average of 6.5 per cent.

Table 2. Tests for the presence of publication bias

	Funnel asymmetry and precision effect tests (FAT-PET)	Precision-effect estimation with standard errors (PEESE)
β_1 (coefficient on $1/SE$ or $1/SE^2$)	-1.679*** [0.143]	-15.859*** [2.491]
β_0 (constant)	-0.024*** [0.001]	-0.032*** [0.001]

Source: authors’ calculations

Graphical visualisation of the funnel asymmetry test is presented in Figure 1. It clearly shows the bias of the mean estimate (red line) towards an increasing penalty compared to the adjusted estimates (green lines for the two adjustment options). The bias is explainable by the fact that in selecting results, authors and editors may favour estimates that are more in line with the currently prevailing concept of the presence of a significant motherhood penalty.

Figure 1. Distribution of estimates of the motherhood penalty depending on their precision. Source: authors’ calculations

Multiple meta-regression analysis

Estimates of the motherhood penalty depend significantly on how they were obtained. The multiple meta-regression analysis provides insight into the direction and size of the effect of the characteristics of econometric modelling of motherhood penalty estimation. We group

them as follows: 1) technical characteristics of the regression model used; 2) method of definition of the motherhood variable; 3) inclusion of various variables controlling for individual characteristics of a woman and her employment in the model; 4) the use of a specific subsample; 5) country of estimation; and 6) estimation period. The results of the regression analysis are presented in Table 3. More detailed information, including the values of standard errors, may be found in the Annex (Table A2).

Let us explain the aspects of interpretation of the results obtained. Since the presence of the motherhood penalty corresponds to a situation where the regression coefficient on the motherhood variable is significant and negative, the significant negative coefficients on another factor in the meta-regression indicate that this factor contributes to the increase, while significant positive coefficients contribute to the decrease of the motherhood penalty estimate.

We use three estimation models to test the robustness of the results: the least-squares method with weighting by estimation error; the least-squares method with weighting by citations and error clustering; and the least-squares method with fixed effects of the publications from which the estimates are drawn. We consider the last of these three models to be optimal (Stanley and Doucouliagos 2012; de Linde Leonard and Stanley 2020). We consider as robust those estimates that have a significant effect with a constant sign for all the three models, or for the two models if one of them is the third model, i.e. the one we consider optimal.

Technical characteristics of the motherhood penalty estimation model

Using a regression model with fixed effects increases the motherhood penalty (for model 3, which we consider optimal in our analysis). A similar effect is observed for other regression models that take into account the panel structure of data. This suggests that controlling for unobservable characteristics, including those related to performance, does not even partially explain the existing motherhood penalty. The authors of an earlier meta-review of the motherhood penalty (de Linde Leonard and Stanley 2020) came to a similar conclusion. Thus, the penalty cannot be explained by lower labour productivity of women with children due to unobservable factors. This leads to the conclusion that the concept of relatively lower productivity of mothers (the first part of the labour effort concept) is not supported by our calculations.

The size of the motherhood penalty estimate is also affected by how wages are measured (see also Figure A2 in the Annex). We looked at the hourly wages compared to all other methods of measurement (daily, monthly, annual) and found that including the hourly wages in the model significantly reduces the penalty estimate. This finding is repeatedly found in other studies, too, including in the meta-analysis of the gender wage gap (de Linde Leonard and Stanley 2020). There is a similar logic here: women compared to men, like mothers compared to other women, work fewer hours on average. Therefore, the concept of relatively low working hours of mothers (the second part of the labour effort concept, after productivity) is confirmed.

At the same time, the variable of selection (into motherhood or into employment) was significantly positive (reducing the penalty estimate) for two out of the three models. This suggests a certain selection of women in connection with both the decision to take up employment and the choice of such a job, industry, occupation, education, career path that will allow combining family and work responsibilities with a detriment to the size of wages. The concept of compensating differentials is confirmed.

The meta-analysis confirmed the assumption (see also Figure A2 in the Annex) that the estimated penalty depends on the definition of motherhood. In particular, it was shown that, taking other factors into account, the motherhood penalty is higher for women with two or more children compared to women with one child, and compared to estimates obtained from models that defined motherhood as a fact of having children without specifying their number.

Incorporating specific factors of the motherhood penalty into the estimation model

Much of the variation in the existing estimates of the motherhood penalty can be explained by controlling for women's individual characteristics in the regression models. Including factors such as race or ethnicity, age, marital status, education, tenure (time at last job), employment interruptions, hours worked, type of employer ownership, size of business, and information on the region and type of locality of residence has a significant effect on the penalty estimate. Generally, accounting for individual characteristics reduces the penalty estimate by explaining part of the wage differential between mothers and other women. In particular, this is true for education, which is further confirmed by a lower penalty for the subsample of less educated women (the regression coefficient on this variable was found to be significant and positive). Thus, in terms of education attained, most of the wage inequality between mothers and other women is explained by intergroup differences, that is, differences in wages between women with high and low levels of education. The situation is similar for the marital status: including the respective information in the model, all other things being equal, contributes to a lower penalty, while the estimates for the subsamples of married or single women are also lower. Apart from the education and marital status, inclusion in the model of characteristics of employment (work experience, employment interruptions, hours worked) and the woman's employer (size and industry) explains part of the penalty (and contributes to its reduction). The effect of age is further supported by the results for subsample estimates, namely a higher penalty for younger women.

However, there are a few exceptions. In contrast, inclusion in the model of information on race or ethnicity, age, region of residence, and whether the woman works for a public or private employer or is informally employed does contribute to the penalty. It can be hypothesised that for these factors, there is a higher intra-group wage inequality between mothers and other women. In particular, this effect was found for wage inequality in Latin America: it was determined more by inequality within gender or ethnic groups than by intergroup differences (Cunningham and Jacobsen 2008).

Subsampling can also have an impact on the penalty. For example, including only young women or women with full-time jobs in the sample increases the penalty. If only women with a low level of education are selected, the penalty tends to decrease. The penalty also decreases if we rely on subsamples based on marital status, i.e. if we consider only married or only single women.

One of the aims of our study was to maximise the geographical spread of motherhood penalty estimates. In total, the final study sample contained 38 countries. This allowed the model to include dummy variables for seven groups of countries, including parts of Europe (Southern, Western, Northern, and Central and Eastern), the USA, other developed English-speaking countries (Australia, Canada, Ireland, UK), and Latin America.

The eighth group – other countries in the sample, including Southeast Asia (China, Japan, South Korea), India, Turkey, and South Africa – was used as the reference against which comparisons were made. Unfortunately, due to an insufficient number of observations, we were not able to divide the heterogeneous group of the remaining countries (as can be seen in particular from the density plot of the distribution of motherhood penalty estimates for this group compared to the others, see Figure A2 in the Annex) into several more homogeneous groups. However, judging by the growing interest in the motherhood penalty in these countries, it is safe to assume that such an opportunity would arise in the near future.

According to our calculations, given the publication bias and specificity of calculations, the penalty estimates for most regional groups of European countries are indistinguishable from other countries, except for Western Europe. Expectedly, the highest penalty was observed in the USA, followed by Western Europe, while relatively low penalties were observed in Latin America. The results for the USA and Western Europe are in line with the results of the earlier meta-studies of motherhood penalty (Cukrowska-Torzewska, Matysiak, 2020; de Linde Leonard, Stanley, 2020). In terms of the estimates obtained, it is 1.8-3.4 p.p. higher than the group average for the rest of countries. It should be noted that the unadjusted (simple) average motherhood penalty is higher in Eastern and Central Europe and Latin America (Figure A1). However, the average precision of these estimates is lower, and as a result they are assigned a lower weight in the meta-regression analysis.

Including information on the period of estimation in the model allows to evaluate the variation over time of the size of motherhood penalty, given the various features of its estimation. It is difficult to do this directly, as a large share of the available estimates were obtained for long panel data series extending over several decades. Therefore, the temporal effect becomes less discernible over long periods of observations. We partly solved this problem by including in the model the decade with a midpoint of the observation period used in the estimation. Initially, we divided the sample into four groups by the timing of the midpoint of the observation period: the 1980s and before (the omitted category); the 1990s, the 2000s, the 2010s and later. However, the procedure of step-by-step exclusion of insignificant variables (the general-to-specific method) still kept two variables with information about the last two decades in the model. In such a situation, the comparison is made with all the earlier periods (i.e. before 2000). The penalty has been declining every decade since the 2000s.

Table 3. Results of the multiple meta-analysis of the motherhood penalty

	WLS [1/SE]	WLS [1/SE] + citations.	Fixed effects
<i>Model (the missing category: OLS)</i>			
Fixed effects	-0.020***	-0.012**	-0.007***
Other panel methods	-0.007*	-0.011	-0.010**
<i>Accounting for selectivity</i>			
Selection procedure (any)	0.005**	0.002	0.004*
<i>Method of wage estimation (the missing category: daily, monthly, annual)</i>			
Hourly wage	0.039***	0.042***	0.032***

	WLS [1/SE]	WLS [1/SE] + citations.	Fixed effects
<i>Method of determining motherhood (the missing category: a minimum of two children)</i>			
Presence of children	0.030***	0.025***	0.009***
Number of children	0.043***	0.040***	0.032***
One child	0.045***	0.042***	0.036***
<i>Inclusion of specific variables in the model</i>			
Race / ethnicity	-0.014***	-0.013*	-0.005*
Age	-0.029***	-0.028***	-0.013***
Region	-0.019***	-0.023***	-0.031***
Type of settlement	0.012***	0.021***	0.027***
Marital status	0.022***	0.013**	0.015***
Other household characteristics	0.008**	0.011	0.023***
Education	0.009***	0.014*	0.005*
Tenure	0.007***	0.005	0.005**
Employment interruptions	0.019***	0.023***	0.032***
Occupation	0.005*	0.000	0.013***
Industry	0.007***	0.01	0.016***
Employer size	0.011***	0.010*	0.004*
Hours worked	0.011***	0.015**	0.006***
Type of employer ownership (public / private)	-0.012***	-0.012	-0.029***
Informal employment	-0.017**	0.007	-0.043**
<i>Estimates for selected groups of women</i>			
Only young women	-0.031***	-0.027***	-0.021***
Full-time employees only	-0.012***	-0.017*	-0.033***
Only private sector employees	0.012***	0.01	-0.008*
Only women with a low level of education	0.016**	0.016*	0.005
Only married women	0.035***	0.018**	0.030***
Only single women	0.019***	0.015***	0.012**
<i>Groups of countries</i>			
Western Europe	-0.018***	-0.017	-0.018***
USA	-0.019***	-0.021**	-0.034***
Latin America	0.029***	0.042**	0.043***
<i>Midpoint of the observation period</i>			
the 2000s	0.006***	0.006	0.016***
the 2010s	0.017***	0.017	0.037***
estimation error (SE)	-0.800***	-0.907**	-1.121***
Constant	-0.089***	-0.088***	-0.073***
N	2055	2055	2055

Source: authors' calculations

Note: ***, **, * stand for significance at 1, 5, and 10% level, respectively.

Conclusion and discussion

This paper presents the results of the meta-analysis of the available estimates of motherhood penalty. More specifically, we were interested in women's wage differentials depending on whether they have children or how many children, if any. Conventionally, the motherhood penalty is estimated using the value of the coefficient on the motherhood variable in a standard regression model of the logarithm of wages for women.

With the growing number of empirical research available on similar areas, there is a growing relevance of quantitative literature reviews analysing similar estimates, which nevertheless differ significantly in terms of their characteristics of calculations and the data on which they were obtained. At the same time, the technical and methodological apparatus of meta-studies is developing rapidly, primarily through the use of the methods of regression analysis.

In the course of the study, we applied the most extensive search procedure for relevant studies available in aggregators of scholarly publications. Then, based on the results of the search, we built a quantitative study database, including, along with the estimates of the motherhood penalty and their precision per se, a wide range of technical characteristics and information on the specification of the estimation model and on its major factors of motherhood penalty. We then conducted a meta-regression analysis of the collected data, which allowed to eliminate the bias caused by publication selectivity and heterogeneity of estimates, and to identify possible mechanisms of motherhood penalty.

Publication bias is a major problem in calculating the mean value of the estimated effect (in our case, the motherhood penalty). It appears that papers with relatively higher estimates of the penalty are more likely to be published – when reviewing the papers containing relatively low precision of estimates (i.e., with a relatively high error), editors are more inclined to reject those with lower penalty estimates than those that infer a higher, relative to the mean, penalty value. Another, perhaps an even more widespread, reason is authors' self-censorship, where, out of several estimation options, they choose as their "clean" estimate the one that is more consistent with the currently prevailing theory (in our case, it is the presence of a significant motherhood penalty).

Based on the results obtained (FAT-PET and PEESE tests), we conclude that there is a significant publication bias in the estimation of motherhood penalty. However, even with this in mind, the motherhood penalty remains significant at 2.4-3.2% depending on the test. Our calculations confirm the results of earlier reviews of the motherhood penalty (Cukrowska-Torzewska and Matysiak 2020; de Linde Leonard and Stanley 2020).

Apart from the estimation precision, there are many other sources of heterogeneity of the existing estimates of motherhood penalty. The first group of factors includes technical characteristics of the estimation model. Researchers may use simple OLS (least squares method) estimates or models that take into account the panel structure of data, they may or may not include information on selection into employment or into motherhood, or differently define the dependent variable in the wage equation (wages per hour, per day, per month or per year). Much depends on which variable is used to measure the motherhood effect (presence of children, number of children, variables for a certain number of children).

Our calculations have confirmed the significance of the technical characteristics of the model. The estimate size is significantly affected by the accounting for the panel structure of data and selection into employment, the method of determining the motherhood variable, and the method of measuring wages.

It is worth noting the difficulties in interpreting the results for panel data estimates as model limitations. It appears that there is a lack of clarity regarding the distinction between models with fixed effects and models on pooled data over a number of years in the reviewed papers. Consequently, the “true” fixed effects may not be clearly determined.

There is another important aspect to this discussion. The use of panel regressions changes the treatment of motherhood variables. For example, instead of the variable “number of children,” effectively its increment is considered compared to the data of the previous round of survey, namely the fact of having a child. For the variables of the presence of a specific number of children, it would be, accordingly, the fact of the birth of a child of a given birth order. The effect of such an event is diminished. The method of motherhood measurement is an important factor in estimating the penalty. Where this includes information on the birth of a first child (in our model, it is one child, presence of children, number of children), such estimates yield a lower penalty compared with the variables related to the birth of a second and any subsequent child.

Another source of heterogeneity is the inclusion or non-inclusion of various individual or employment characteristics of women in the motherhood penalty estimation model. A significant reduction in the motherhood penalty estimate in the event that human capital characteristics are included in the model suggests an effect of losses associated with employment interruptions and underinvestment in the human capital of women who are more likely to commit themselves to motherhood (Mincer and Polachek 1974; Polachek 1981). The significance of employment characteristics for the motherhood penalty estimation may suggest that mothers tend to exchange part of their earnings for more convenient working conditions (Becker 1985; Goldin 2014).

Comparison of the size of the motherhood penalty across different groups of countries is another important focus of our research. In the course of analysis, we tested several typologies of countries for which estimates of the motherhood penalty are available, including those related to the grouping of countries by their per capita GDP or depending on which model of social policy and welfare state the countries follow. Due to the nature of our sample, which is dominated by the USA and Europe, while the estimates for other countries are not numerous enough to be further disaggregated, we settled on a typology of countries based on their fertility rates and gender wage differentials. As a result, we included the following groups of countries in the final version of the regression model: 1) Western Europe (Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Switzerland), 2) Central and Eastern Europe (Czechia, Hungary, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Ukraine), 3) Northern Europe (Denmark, Finland, Norway, Sweden), 4) Southern Europe (Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain), 5) the USA, 6) other English-speaking countries (Australia, Canada, Ireland, UK); 7) Latin America (Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Ecuador, Mexico, Peru); 8) other countries (China, India, Japan, South Africa, South Korea, Turkey).

We believe that the penalty size may be influenced by the country’s fertility pattern, which in turn determines the prevailing type of discrimination against women in a given country’s labour market. Our hypothesis is that in regions with a low gender wage gap, the motherhood penalty may be higher. The opposite is also true: where the gender wage gap is large, the motherhood penalty may not be that high because employers, by imposing the penalty on all women, do not need to further discriminate against female workers with children relative to women without children of a certain age. The heterogeneity of distribution of women by the ultimate number of children born may serve as a medium in this relationship “gender gap – motherhood penalty” (Kalabikhina and Kuznetsova 2023). High heterogeneity corresponds to a higher motherhood penalty (and a low gender pay gap). Low heterogeneity

of women by the total number of children born corresponds to a lower motherhood penalty (and a relatively high gender pay gap). High heterogeneity is found where the numbers of both childless women and women with three or more children are relatively high.

Figure 2 presents the evolution of fertility heterogeneity using childlessness as an example. The authors drew the information on ultimate childlessness in different female cohorts throughout most of the twentieth century from the following three sources of fertility data: IPUMSI census data (Minnesota Population Center 2020), CFE fertility and education data (Zeman et al. 2017), and data from the international Human Fertility Database (HFD) (Human Fertility Database 2024). Only countries included in our sample of motherhood penalty estimates were considered. Fertility data are presented for cohorts of women ordered by the year of birth. In terms of comparison with the results of the analysis of motherhood penalty estimates, we are most interested in the period from the 1970s to the 2010s, which corresponds to the cohorts of women born since the 1930s.

The figure clearly shows that for the generations born in the 1930s–1960s, the childless rate in Eastern and Central Europe, Latin America, and most other countries (red, yellow, and grey lines) is lower than in the English-speaking countries and Western Europe (green and solid blue lines). For the subsequent generations represented in the right-hand side of the figure, the situation changes: childlessness rises sharply in South-East Asia and in some Eastern European countries, notably Poland and Hungary. Nevertheless, we can conclude that for most of the period of interest, Western Europe and the USA stood out from many other countries in terms of their higher fertility heterogeneity and, in particular, childlessness, which may explain, at least in part, both a lower gender wage gap and a higher motherhood penalty. With higher heterogeneity in fertility, it is disadvantageous for employers to adopt a one-size-fits-all approach to all women; not all women will become mothers. The notion of statistical discrimination against women is untenable, but discrimination against mothers is likely to increase, resulting in a relatively higher motherhood penalty.

Another important result related to the regional factor should be mentioned. According to our estimates, the motherhood penalty increases when information on the women's region of

Figure 2. Evolution of ultimate childlessness by regional groups of countries. *Source:* Authors' calculations based on IPUMSI (Minnesota Population Center 2020), CFE (Zeman et al. 2017), HFD (Human Fertility Database 2024).

residence is included in the regression model. This variable is usually missing in the studies using data for smaller countries. In our view, this result can be explained by the scale effect: women’s wage differentials depending on the motherhood status may, all other things being equal, be higher in countries with marked regional differentiation and income inequality.

The evolution of the motherhood penalty over time is also of interest. How does the motherhood penalty change at different stages of labour market development in general and female employment in particular? Initially, before the mass entry of women into the labour market, the motherhood penalty was most likely low. In the absence of mass female employment, the labour market at that time had not formed a ‘response’ to the combination of motherhood and employment. Then the penalty increased as the phenomenon of mass female employment emerged, but at first it was unregulated discrimination, as there was not yet an institutional response in place to counteract the infringement of the rights of some workers. The penalty then begins to decrease as the gender component of the policy is activated and institutions emerge for the protection of women’s rights and reduction of discrimination of women with children in the labour market. Thus, if the empirical base of a study includes the initial period when women’s employment was not yet widespread, it can be assumed that the dependence of the penalty on time would have an inverted U-shape.

Figure 3 presents World Bank data on the evolution of women’s economic activity in the countries included in the meta-analysis of motherhood penalty over the last sixty years. Information on the earliest period, up to the second half of the 1970s, is unfortunately fragmentary, yet it does indicate that the phenomenon of mass female employment was exclusive to the countries of the communist bloc, while in the English-speaking and Scandinavian countries it grew rapidly starting from a very low base. The growth of women’s employment in Western and Southern Europe, and especially in Latin America, started even later, but it was rapid, and by the 1990s, a broadly modern situation with women’s mass economic activity had already emerged.

Our meta-review of the motherhood penalty was only able to see the right-hand, later part of the inverted U-shaped relationship between the penalty and the time of observation. Estimates of the motherhood penalty in samples whose midpoints occurred in the 2000s and 2010s

Figure 3. Evolution of economic activity of women aged 15 and over by regional groups of countries. Source. World Bank Gender Statistics, <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/gender-statistics>

are significantly lower than the rest. For future research, it is important to note that the women's mass entry into the labour market occurred at different times in different countries, including the periods that are outside the scope of existing estimates of the motherhood penalty.

Funding

The study was carried out within the framework of the research project "Population reproduction in socio-economic development".

List of references

- Agüero J, Marks MS, Raykar N (2012) The wage penalty for motherhood in developing countries. University of California and Colgate University. URL: https://conference.nber.org/confer/2013/CHEDs13/Aguero_Marks_Raykar.pdf
- Agüero JM, Marks M, Raykar N (2020) Economic development and the motherhood wage penalty. Working Paper 220–06. University of Connecticut, Department of Economics. URL: <https://media.economics.uconn.edu/working/2020-06.pdf>
- Angelov N, Johansson P, Lindahl E (2016) Parenthood and the gender gap in pay. *Journal of Labor Economics* 34(3): 545–79. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/684851>
- Becker GS (1985) Human capital, effort, and the sexual division of labor. *Journal of Labor Economics* 3(1): 33–58. <https://doi.org/10.1086/298075>
- Bianchi SM, Milkie MA, Sayer LC, Robinson JP (2000) Is anyone doing the housework? Trends in the gender division of household labor. *Social Forces* 79(1): 191–228. <https://doi.org/10.1093/SF/79.1.191>
- Black SE, Strahan PE (2001) The division of spoils: rent-sharing and discrimination in a regulated industry. *American Economic Review* 91(4): 814–31. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.91.4.814>
- Blau FD, Brummund P, Liu AY (2013) Trends in Occupational Segregation by Gender 1970– 2009: Adjusting for the Impact of Changes in the Occupational Coding System. *Demography* 50: 471–92. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13524-012-0151-7>
- Blau FD, Kahn LM (2017) The gender wage gap: Extent, trends, and explanations. *Journal of Economic Literature* 55(3): 789–865. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.20160995>
- Budig MJ, England P (2001) The wage penalty for motherhood. *American Sociological Review* 66(2): 204–25. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000312240106600203>
- Budig MJ, Hodges MJ (2010) Differences in disadvantage: Variation in the motherhood penalty across white women's earnings distribution. *American Sociological Review* 75(5): 705–28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0003122410381593>
- Budig MJ, Misra J, Boeckmann I (2016) Work–family policy trade-offs for mothers? Unpacking the cross-national variation in motherhood earnings penalties. *Work and Occupations* 43(2): 119–77. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0730888415615385>
- Cain GG (1986) The economic analysis of labor market discrimination: A survey. In: *Handbook of Labor Economics*: 1: 693–785. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1573-4463\(86\)01016-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1573-4463(86)01016-7)
- Correll SJ, Benard S, Paik I (2007) Getting a job: Is there a motherhood penalty? *American Journal of Sociology* 112(5): 1297–338. <https://doi.org/10.1086/511799>
- Cortés P, Pan J (2018) Occupation and gender. IZA Discussion Paper: 10672. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2949108>

- Cortés P, Pan J (2023) Children and the remaining gender gaps in the labor market. *Journal of Economic Literature* 61(4): 1359–409. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.20221549>
- Cuberes D, Newiak M, Teignier M (2016) Gender inequality and macroeconomic performance. In: K Kochhar, S Jain-Chandra, M Newiak (eds.) *Women, work, and economic growth: Leveling the playing field*. International Monetary Fund, Washington, DC, 31–48. URL: <https://www.elibrary.imf.org/display/book/9781513516103/9781513516103.xml>
- Cuddy AJ, Fiske ST, Glick P (2004) When professionals become mothers, warmth doesn't cut the ice. *Journal of Social Issues* 60(4): 701–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0022-4537.2004.00381.x>
- Cukrowska-Torzewska E, Lovasz A (2020) The role of parenthood in shaping the gender wage gap – A comparative analysis of 26 European countries. *Social Science Research* 85: 102355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2019.102355>
- Cukrowska-Torzewska E, Matysiak A (2020) The motherhood wage penalty: A meta-analysis. *Social Science Research* 88–89: 102416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2020.102416>
- Cunningham W, Jacobsen JP (2008) Earnings inequality within and across gender, racial, and ethnic groups in four Latin American countries. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper: 4591. URL: <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/904671468005421981/earnings-inequality-within-and-across-gender-racial-and-ethnic-groups-in-four-latin-american-countries>
- de Linde Leonard M, Stanley TD (2020) The wages of mothers' labor: A meta-regression analysis. *Journal of Marriage and Family* 82(5): 1534–52. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12693>
- Flabbi L (2010) Gender discrimination estimation in a search model with matching and bargaining. *International Economic Review* 51(3): 745–83. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2354.2010.00600.x>
- Gallen Y (2024) Motherhood and the gender productivity gap. *Journal of the European Economic Association* 22(3): 1055–96. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jeea/jvad064>
- Gangl M, Ziefle A (2009) Motherhood, labor force behavior, and women's careers: An empirical assessment of the wage penalty for motherhood in Britain, Germany, and the United States. *Demography* 46: 341–69. <https://doi.org/10.1353/dem.0.0056>
- Glass J (2004) Blessing or curse? Work-family policies and mother's wage growth over time. *Work and Occupations* 31(3): 367–94. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0730888404266364>
- Goldin C (2014) A grand gender convergence: Its last chapter. *American Economic Review* 104(4): 1091–119. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.104.4.1091>
- Gough O (2001) The impact of the gender pay gap on post-retirement earnings. *Critical Social Policy* 21(3): 311–34. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026101830102100303>
- Gradín C, del Río C, Cantó O (2010) Gender wage discrimination and poverty in the EU. *Feminist Economics* 16(2): 73–109. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701003731831>
- Jessen J (2022) Culture, children and couple gender inequality. *European Economic Review* 150: 104310. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.euroecorev.2022.104310>
- Kalabikhina IE, Kuznetsova PO (2023) Population Heterogeneity in the Number of Children Born: Is There a “Parity Transition”? *Monitoring of Public Opinion: Economic and Social Changes* 2(174): 57–81. <https://doi.org/10.14515/monitoring.2023.2.2362> (in Russian)
- Karabchuk T, Trach T, Pankratova V (2021) Motherhood wage penalty in Russia: Empirical study on RLMS-HSE data. In: T Karabchuk, K Kumo, K Gatskova, E Skoglund (eds.) *Gendering Post-Soviet Space: Demography, Labor Market and Values in Empirical Research*. Springer, Singapore, 235–55. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-9358-1_11
- Kelley H, Galbraith Q, Strong J (2020) Working moms: Motherhood penalty or motherhood return? *The Journal of Academic Librarianship* 46(1): 102075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2019.102075>
- Klepinger D, Lundberg S, Plotnick R (1999) How does adolescent fertility affect the human capital and wages of young women? *Journal of Human Resources* 34(3): 421–48. <https://doi.org/10.2307/146375>

- Kleven H, Landais C, Sogaard JE (2019) Children and gender inequality: Evidence from Denmark. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics* 11(4): 181–209. <https://doi.org/10.1257/app.20180010>
- Levanon A, Grusky DB (2016) The persistence of extreme gender segregation in the twenty-first century. *American Journal of Sociology* 122(2): 573–619. <https://doi.org/10.1086/688628>
- Lundberg S, Rose E (2000) Parenthood and the earnings of married men and women. *Labour Economics* 7(6): 689–710. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0927-5371\(00\)00020-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0927-5371(00)00020-8)
- Mincer J, Polachek S (1974) Family investments in human capital: Earnings of women. *Journal of Political Economy* 82(2): S76–S108. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1829993>
- Nielsen HS, Simonsen M, Verner M (2004) Does the gap in family-friendly policies drive the family gap? *The Scandinavian Journal of Economics* 106(4): 721–44. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0347-0520.2004.00385.x>
- Oshchepkov Yu (2006) Gender wage gap in Russia // Higher School of Economics Economic Journal 10(4): 590–619. URL: https://ej.hse.ru/data/2010/12/31/1208184729/10_04_03.pdf (in Russian)
- Pan J (2015) Gender segregation in occupations: The role of tipping and social interactions. *Journal of Labor Economic* 33(2): 365–408. <https://doi.org/10.1086/678518>
- Polachek SW (1981) Occupational self-selection: A human capital approach to sex differences in occupational structure. *The Review of Economics and Statistics* 63(1): 60–9. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1924218>
- Stanley TD (2008) Meta-regression methods for detecting and estimating empirical effects in the presence of publication selection. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics* 70(1): 103–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0084.2007.00487.x>
- Stanley TD, Doucouliagos H (2012) *Meta-regression analysis in economics and business*. Routledge Advances in Research Methods.
- Stanley TD, Doucouliagos H (2014) Meta-regression approximations to reduce publication selection bias. *Research Synthesis Methods* 5(1): 60–78. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1095>
- Stanley TD, Doucouliagos H (2017) Neither fixed nor random: Weighted least squares meta-regression. *Research Synthesis Methods* 8(1): 19–42. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1211>
- Stanley TD, Jarrell SB (1998) Gender wage discrimination bias? A meta-regression analysis. *The Journal of Human Resources* 33(4): 947–73. <https://doi.org/10.2307/146404>
- Strengmann-Kuhn W (2007) Inequalities in Earnings and Child Rearing: What is the Gender Aspect of Poverty? *European Journal of Economics and Economic Policies* 4(1): 175–94. <https://doi.org/10.4337/ejeep.2007.01.12>
- Wang H, Cheng Z (2021) Mama loves you: The gender wage gap and expenditure on children's education in China. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization* 188: 1015–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebo.2021.06.031>
- Warren T, Rowlingson K, Whyley C (2001) Female finances: Gender wage gaps and gender assets gaps. *Work, Employment and Society* 15(3): 465–88. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0950017001000319>

Other sources of information

- Human Fertility Database. Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research (Germany) and Vienna Institute of Demography (Austria). URL: www.humanfertility.org (data downloaded on 1.02.2024).
- Minnesota Population Center (2020) Integrated Public Use Microdata Series, International: Version 7.3 [dataset]. Minneapolis, MN: IPUMS. <https://doi.org/10.18128/D020.V7.3>
- World Bank Gender Statistics. <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/gender-statistics>
- Zeman K, Brzozowska Z, Sobotka T, Beaujouan E, Matysiak A (2017) Cohort Fertility and Education Database. Methods Protocol. Vienna Institute of Demography. URL: www.cfe-database.org (accessed on 1.02.2024).

Annex

Figure A1. Average penalty size and average standard error of estimation by regional groups. *Source:* authors' calculations

Figure A2. Density of distribution of the penalty estimates by subgroups depending on the technical parameters of the regression models and the data source's region. *Source:* authors' calculations

Table A1. Summary statistics of the variables included in the final version of the regression analysis

Variable	Average	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Coefficient on motherhood variable (motherhood penalty estimate)	-0.0654	0.0809	-0.59	0.231
Estimation error	0.029	0.0358	0.001	0.69
Estimation model: with fixed effects	0.33	0.47	0	1
Estimation model: other panel methods	0.0793	0.27	0	1
Accounting for selectivity (any procedure of selection into employment or motherhood)	0.214	0.41	0	1
Wage: hourly	0.804	0.397	0	1
Motherhood variable: presence of children	0.289	0.453	0	1
Motherhood variable: number of children	0.226	0.419	0	1
Motherhood variable: one child	0.182	0.386	0	1
Presence of variable: race/ethnicity	0.285	0.451	0	1
Presence of variable: age	0.75	0.433	0	1
Presence of variable: region of the country	0.265	0.441	0	1
Presence of variable: type of settlement	0.194	0.395	0	1
Presence of variable: marital status	0.777	0.417	0	1
Presence of variable: other household characteristics	0.126	0.332	0	1
Presence of variable: education	0.797	0.403	0	1
Presence of variable: tenure	0.299	0.458	0	1
Presence of variable: employment interruptions	0.117	0.321	0	1
Presence of variable: occupation	0.33	0.47	0	1
Presence of variable: industry	0.216	0.411	0	1
Existence of variable: employer size	0.0915	0.288	0	1
Presence of variable: hours worked	0.423	0.494	0	1
Presence of variable: type of employer ownership	0.291	0.455	0	1
Presence of variable: informal employment	0.0234	0.151	0	1
Sample limitation: young women	0.247	0.431	0	1
Sampling limitation: full-time employment	0.0642	0.245	0	1
Sample limitation: private sector employer	0.0584	0.235	0	1
Sample limitation: low level of education	0.0292	0.168	0	1
Sample limitations: married women	0.035	0.184	0	1
Sample limitations: single women	0.0253	0.157	0	1
Region: Western Europe	0.143	0.35	0	1
Region: USA	0.382	0.486	0	1
Region: Latin America	0.0618	0.241	0	1
Midpoint of the observation period: the 2000s	0.345	0.475	0	1
Midpoint of the observation period: the 2010s	0.092	0.289	0	1

Source: authors' calculations

Table A2. Results of the multiple regression meta-analysis (the dependent variable: coefficient on the motherhood variable in the female wage equation)

	NWLS	WLS [1/SE]	WLS [1/SE] + citations	RE	FE
<i>Model (missing category: OLS)</i>					
Fixed effects	-0.019*** (-4.91)	-0.020*** (-9.14)	-0.012** (-2.32)	-0.011*** (-4.69)	-0.007*** (-3.17)
Other panel methods	-0.007 (-1.00)	-0.007* (-1.86)	-0.011 (-1.33)	-0.005 (-1.38)	-0.010** (-2.34)
<i>Accounting for selectivity</i>					
Selection procedure (any)	0.001 -0.27	0.005** -2.28	0.002 -0.66	0.005** -2.12	0.004* -1.7
<i>Method of wage estimation (missing category: daily, monthly, annual)</i>					
Hourly wage	0.010** -2.03	0.039*** -10.64	0.042*** -2.74	0.053*** -10.62	0.032*** -5.05
<i>Method of determining motherhood (missing category: a minimum of two children)</i>					
Presence of children	0.050*** -11.61	0.030*** -10.22	0.025*** -2.64	0.014*** -4.35	0.009*** -2.69
Number of children	0.051*** -11.26	0.043*** -15.24	0.040*** -3.67	0.040*** -13.94	0.032*** -10.2
One child	0.052*** -12.03	0.045*** -14.68	0.042*** -4.17	0.040*** -14.34	0.036*** -13.25
<i>Presence of specific variables in the model</i>					
Race / ethnicity	-0.015*** (-3.40)	-0.014*** (-4.64)	-0.013* (-1.94)	-0.008*** (-2.68)	-0.005* (-1.79)
Age	-0.009* (-1.94)	-0.029*** (-10.84)	-0.028*** (-3.72)	-0.027*** (-7.59)	-0.013*** (-2.87)
Region of the country	0.012** -2.37	-0.019*** (-6.66)	-0.023*** (-3.61)	-0.026*** (-6.92)	-0.031*** (-6.64)
Type of settlement	0.005 -0.92	0.012*** -3.12	0.021*** -2.69	0.021*** -4.54	0.027*** -5.04
Marital status	0 (-0.02)	0.022*** -8.38	0.013** -2.32	0.021*** -6.98	0.015*** -4.46
Other household characteristics	-0.011* (-1.96)	0.008** -2.24	0.011 -0.91	0.019*** -4.38	0.023*** -5.19
Education	-0.001 (-0.17)	0.009*** -3.17	0.014* -1.94	0.007** -2.38	0.005* -1.77
Tenure	0.028*** -6.62	0.007*** -3.73	0.005 -1.42	0.005** -2.49	0.005** -2.4
Employment interruptions	0.009* -1.72	0.019*** -5.48	0.023*** -2.78	0.029*** -7.9	0.032*** -8.6
Occupation	0.008* -1.81	0.005* -1.8	0.000 (-0.00)	0.011*** -3.93	0.013*** -4.79

	NWLS	WLS [1/SE]	WLS [1/SE] + citations	RE	FE
Industry	0.015*** -2.99	0.007*** -2.78	0.01 -1.27	0.013*** -4.14	0.016*** -5.11
Employer size	-0.014** (-2.34)	0.011*** -4.28	0.010* -1.93	0.006*** -2.74	0.004* -1.87
Hours worked	0.016*** -3.98	0.011*** -6.32	0.015** -2.44	0.009*** -4.89	0.006*** -3.25
Type of employer ownership (public / private)	-0.002 (-0.42)	-0.012*** (-3.92)	-0.012 (-1.34)	-0.024*** (-7.33)	-0.029*** (-8.43)
Informal employment	-0.016 (-1.44)	-0.017** (-2.09)	0.007 -0.55	-0.01 (-0.86)	-0.043** (-2.42)
<i>Estimates for selected groups of women</i>					
Only young women	-0.022*** (-4.72)	-0.031*** (-10.07)	-0.027*** (-3.55)	-0.027*** (-6.43)	-0.021*** (-4.54)
Only full-time employment	-0.01 (-1.49)	-0.012*** (-3.17)	-0.017* (-1.92)	-0.025*** (-6.15)	-0.033*** (-7.74)
Only private sector employees	-0.008 (-1.02)	0.012*** -2.91	0.01 -1.04	0.001 -0.32	-0.008* (-1.77)
Only workers with a low level of education	0.018* -1.86	0.016** -2.35	0.016* -1.7	0.005 -0.91	0.005 -0.83
Only married women	0.019* -1.94	0.035*** -6.62	0.018** -2.29	0.033*** -6.55	0.030*** -5.86
Only single women	0.014 -1.31	0.019*** -3.78	0.015*** -2.84	0.015*** -3.21	0.012** -2.5
<i>Groups of countries</i>					
Western Europe	-0.019*** (-3.62)	-0.018*** (-3.80)	-0.017 (-1.52)	-0.018*** (-3.23)	-0.018*** (-2.88)
USA	-0.021*** (-4.64)	-0.019*** (-5.98)	-0.021** (-2.58)	-0.029*** (-7.25)	-0.034*** (-7.55)
Latin America	0.015* -1.89	0.029*** -4.33	0.042** -2.17	0.038*** -4.93	0.043*** -5.4
<i>Midpoint of observation period (missing category: the 1990s and before)</i>					
the 2000s	-0.006 (-1.55)	0.006*** -2.67	0.006 -0.74	0.012*** -4.81	0.016*** -6.36
the 2010s	-0.007 (-1.10)	0.017*** -4.46	0.017 -1.45	0.031*** -8.29	0.037*** -9.77
estimation error (SE)	-0.903*** (-19.21)	-0.800*** (-5.90)	-0.907** (-2.30)	-1.564*** (-5.46)	-1.121*** (-7.19)

	NWLS	WLS [1/SE]	WLS [1/SE] + citations	RE	FE
Constant	-0.070*** (-7.85)	-0.089*** (-16.90)	-0.088*** (-3.95)	-0.095*** (-15.14)	-0.073*** (-9.43)
N	2055	2055	2055	2055	

Source: authors' calculations

Note 1. NWLS – unweighted linear regression, WLS – weighted linear regression, citations – accounting for the citation impact of the study from which the estimate is taken, RE – model controlling for random effects of the studies from which the estimate is taken, FE – model controlling for fixed effects of the study from which the estimate is taken.

Note 2. ***, **, * – significance at 1, 5, and 10% level, respectively. Standard errors are given in brackets.

Supplementary material 1

Papers included in the meta-analysis

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.8.e121438.suppl1>

Information about the authors

- Irina Evgenievna Kalabikhina – Doctor of Economics, Head of the Population Department. Faculty of Economics of Lomonosov Moscow State University. Moscow, 119991, Russia. E-mail: ikalabikhina@yandex.ru
- Polina Olegovna Kuznetsova – Candidate of Economics, Leading Researcher. Faculty of Economics of Lomonosov Moscow State University; Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration, Moscow, 119571, Russia. E-mail: polina.kuznetsova29@gmail.com
- Sofiiia Andreevna Zhuravleva – graduate student. Faculty of Economics of Lomonosov Moscow State University. Moscow, 119991, Russia. E-mail: sofi-ra@bk.ru